

"Boosting Sustainable Tourism Development and Capacity of Tourism SMEs through Transnational Cooperation and Knowledge Transfer"

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Benchmarking Sustainability of Selected SMEs

A brief report on baseline and needs of selected SMEs

TOURISME

Boosting Sustainable Tourism Development and Capacity of Tourism SMEs through Transnational Cooperation and Knowledge Transfer

 Co-funded by the COSME Initiative of the European Union

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Nordia Development Agency

Improving sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation and multi-stakeholder engagement

D3.4 – Benchmarking Sustainability of Selected SMEs

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report (Deliverable D3.4) was prepared in the context of Work Package 3 of the European Project – TOURISME: Improving the sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation, and multi-stakeholder engagement.

In the EU, tourism is one of the major economic activities with a high impact on economic growth, employment, and social development, and thus it is a powerful means to pursue broader EU employment and growth objectives. The competitiveness of the European tourism industry is closely linked to its sustainability, which is understood as environmental, economic, and socio-cultural aspects of tourism development. Achieving sustainable tourism development can bring numerous benefits derived from the competitive advantage provided by cost savings and the improvement of the quality of the offer. In this sense, to achieve sustainability and improve competitiveness, TOURISME aims at fostering SMEs' capacities and skills to explore and uptake solutions through a reinforced transnational and cross-sectoral collaboration amongst tourism SMEs and operators in Spain, Italy, France, and Cyprus.

More specifically, the objectives of TOURISME are as follows:

- To design and implement trans-national and cross-sectoral support schemes including capacity building knowledge.
- Transfer and scaling-up activities to enable sustainable growth of SMEs in the tourism sector.
- To support the uptake of innovative solutions for sustainable tourism.
- To support the participation of SMEs in certification schemes.

In doing so, following the amended Grant Agreement, TOURISME aims at selecting and engaging at least 60 SMEs from 3 official project countries (Spain, Italy, and France), plus the additional country of Cyprus, to participate in and potentially benefit from the developed project schemes. In particular, the amended Grant Agreement required at least 20 SMEs in each of the 3 official countries, totaling a minimum of 60 SMEs. The proposed targets for each country by the TOURISME consortium are the following:

- Spain: at least 20 SMEs
- Italy: at least 20 SMEs
- France: at least 20 SMEs
- Cyprus: 3 additional SMEs

A call for SMEs selection was published on the TOURISME website (<https://tourisme-project.eu/call-for-smes>) in June 2021. After the call's deadline, the selection process awarded a total of 55 SMEs, thus failing to reach the required minimum number due to the poor response in Cyprus, where only 3 agreements were signed compared to the originally planned of 12. In agreement with EISMEA, the consortium decided to re-open the call only for SMEs in Cyprus. Unfortunately, no extra SMEs applied to the call. TOURISME was thus converted into a three-country project (France, Italy, and Spain), with the optional participation of Cyprus to create an added value. To compensate for the missing numbers from Cyprus, the reserve lists of the other partner countries were revised and a third call for SMEs only from France, Italy, Spain was launched to get to the pre-established targets. The evaluation committee received a further 12 applications, all of which were eligible.

In total, 65 agreements were signed with SMEs:

- Cyprus: 3 SMEs
- France: 20 SMEs
- Italy: 21 SMEs
- Spain: 21 SMEs

The scope of this report is to highlight the baseline scenario in terms of the sustainability of each selected SME and to elucidate their specific needs. This report would not just serve as an input in tailoring the schemes but also as a reference point for the final assessment foreseen in WP5 to determine the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions.

This report is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) briefly explains the approach used to assess the baseline and needs of tourism SMEs in terms of sustainability. [Section 3](#) provides an aggregated overview of sustainability in selected tourism SMEs i.e., accommodations and travel enterprises participating in the TOURISME project. [Section 4](#) explicates the baseline scenario of each selected tourism SME.

2.METHODOLOGY

The applicants were asked to inform the current status of certifications and sustainability practices in their SMEs. The current status of sustainability and their willingness to transition towards sustainability was one of the main criteria for the selection of SMEs. This information was collected through the survey questionnaire of the call, and it represents the baseline scenario of selected SMEs.

An environmental certification could potentially lead and/or ensure sustainability in an organization. The applicants were, therefore, asked whether they have already adopted EMAS, EU Ecolabel, and ISO certifications such as ISO 9001, ISO 14001, ISO 22000, ISO 50001, ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001. As there are various certifying bodies and schemes in different countries, we also asked applicants to inform whether they have adopted any sector-specific certifications or other certifications recognized in their respective countries.

Applicants were also asked to declare whether they would be interested to access environmental certification. Lastly, applicants were asked to declare whether they have already implemented any of the listed sustainability practices and which sustainability practices they would be interested to implement during the TOURISME project being beneficiary (or selected) SMEs. It is worth mentioning that sustainability practices could vary for accommodations and travel enterprises and therefore two slightly different survey questionnaires were papered.

3.AGGREGATED OVERVIEW OF SUSTAINABILITY

3.1 ISO Certifications, EMAS, and EU Ecolabel

It is not surprising that the current state of certifications is very poor in the selected SMEs. Only 2 out of 36 selected accommodations have adopted ISO 14001, only 2 out of 36 has adopted ISO 9001 and 1 out of 36 is ISO 5001 certified, while the other ISO certifications have not yet been adopted by the selected

accommodations. However, 4 of the 36 selected accommodations have already adopted the EU Ecolabel (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Status of certifications in accommodations

The baseline scenario with regard to certifications is worst in the case of travel companies. In other words, only 1 of the 29 selected travel companies has adopted ISO 9001, while the other ISO certifications have not yet been adopted by the selected travel companies, nor have they yet adopted EMAS or the EU Ecolabel (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Status of certifications in travel enterprises

3.2 Sector Specific Certifications

The situation is also poor concerning national or sector-specific certifications. Only 1 out of 36 accommodations have adopted Legambiente Turismo certification while the rest of the certifications are not considered by 36 selected accommodations (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Status of sector-specific certifications in accommodations

The situation is the same concerning national or sector-specific certifications in the case of travel enterprises. That is, none out of 29 selected travel enterprises have adopted any of the listed certifications (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Status of sector-specific certifications in travel enterprises

3.3 Willingness to Access Certifications

Although most of the selected SMEs do not have adopted any sort of certifications, most of them are willing to participate in activity 3 in order to access certifications. 32 out of 36 selected accommodations have explicitly stated that they are interested to access certifications (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Accommodations willing to participate (or not) in Activity 3

On the other hand, 18 out of 29 selected travel enterprises have expressed their interest to access certifications while 11 selected travel enterprises are not interested in doing so (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Travel enterprises willing to participate (or not) in Activity 3

3.4 Current Status of Sustainability Practices

Most of the selected accommodations have implemented some sort of sustainability practices. The most widely implemented sustainability practices include reducing plastic use, reducing water consumption, reducing energy consumption, and reducing food waste. In contrast, the least implemented practices are the assessment of carbon footprint and reuse of water (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Status of sustainability practices in accommodations

On the other hand, most of the selected travel enterprises have not yet implemented any sort of sustainability practices. The most implemented practices are promoting sustainable mobility and training staff on sustainability issues (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Status of sustainability practices in travel enterprises

3.5 Willingness to Implement Sustainability Practices

The main purpose of the TOURISME project is to support tourism SMEs in transitioning towards sustainability. The selected SMEs have shown their motivation to implement listed sustainability practices. More than 90% of selected accommodations are willing to implement practices linked to Awareness and Behavioral Change, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Energy Conservation, Green Procurement, Sustainable Mobility, Waste Management, and Water Conservation (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Accommodations willing to implement (or not) sustainability practices

Selected travel enterprises, same as accommodations, are also enthusiastic to implement relevant sustainability practices (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Travel enterprises willing to implement (or not) sustainability practices

4. BASELINE SCENARIO OF EACH SME

4.1 Cyprus: Falatzi Touristikes Epichiriseis Ltd

■ Profile:

SME Code	60
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted

Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	No
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	No
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	No
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes

Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.2 Cyprus: Olympia Traditional Houses

■ Profile:

SME Code	120
NACE Code	Other reservation service and related activities (NACE 79.9)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted

BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.3 Cyprus: Travelorama

■ Profile:

SME Code	1
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted

Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.4 France: Revlys

■ Profile:

SME Code	137
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted

ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.5 France: Japan Experience

■ Profile:

SME Code	78
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	11 to 50 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.6 France: Shanti Travel

■ Profile:

SME Code	32
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.7 France: Odysway

■ Profile:

SME Code	80
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
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Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.8 France: Light Trip

■ Profile:

SME Code	119
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes

Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.9 France: SAS Val De Roland

■ Profile:

SME Code	124
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	No
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No

Diversifying its water supply	No
Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.10 France: Discovery Trains

■ Profile:

SME Code	27
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.11 France: MOB HOTEL LYON

■ Profile:

SME Code	100
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes

 Optimizing pool maintenance

 Yes

4.12 France: LA ROUTE DES VOYAGES

■ Profile:

SME Code	102
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.13 France: Nextone Residence

■ Profile:

SME Code	31
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
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Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	No
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	No
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	No
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	No
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	No
	Diversifying its energy sources	No
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	No
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	No
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	No
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.14 France: MOB HOTEL PARIS

■ Profile:

SME Code	92
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes

Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.15 France: VoyagExpérience

■ Profile:

SME Code	106
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.16 France: Pyrène et Compagnie - Gîte de Llo

■ Profile:

SME Code	125
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.17 France: Hotel Cannes Centre Univers

■ Profile:

SME Code	44
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)

Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	No
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
Energy conservation	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	No
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.18 France: La Maison du Bonheur

■ Profile:

SME Code	2 ¹
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

¹ SME Code from the TOURISME third SME call.

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes

Energy conservation	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	No
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	No
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.19 France: Hotel Duo - SA Axial Beaubourg

■ Profile:

SME Code	3 ²
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted

² SME Code from the TOURISME third SME call.

Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes

Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.20 France: Syltours

■ Profile:

SME Code	135
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	11 to 50 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted

BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.21 France: Yogascope

■ Profile:

SME Code	39
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (below - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted

Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.22 France: D TOUR

■ Profile:

SME Code	57
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted

ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.23 France: ALTIPLANO VOYAGE

■ Profile:

SME Code	83
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.24 Italy: Pradelli Gestioni Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	62
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NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	No
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	No
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
Energy conservation	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	No
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	No
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	No
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	No
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	No
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.25 Italy: Limolo House 56 Green

■ Profile:

SME Code	79
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes

Energy conservation	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.26 Italy: La Tinaia di Giovanni Salaris

■ Profile:

SME Code	140
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted

Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	No
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes

Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.27 Italy: Alba Hotels Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	109
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted

BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Knowing its waste volume	Yes

Waste management	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.28 Italy: Grand Hotel Abi D'oru

■ Profile:

SME Code	114
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	50 to 249
Annual Turnover in 2019	11 to 50 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (between - 6% and - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	No
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	No
	Diversifying its energy sources	No
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	No
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	No
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	No
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	No
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No

Diversifying its water supply	No
Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.29 Italy: Turismore Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	10
NACE Code	Other reservation service and related activities (NACE 79.9)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	No
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.30 Italy: Sa. Fa. Pa di Saba Marco & CSas

■ Profile:

SME Code	42
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (between - 6% and - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes

Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes
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4.31 Italy: Hotel Santa Gilla

■ Profile:

SME Code	121
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	No
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes

Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	No
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	No
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.32 Italy: H.G.A Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	126
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	50 to 249
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	No
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	No
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	No
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	No
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	No
	Preventing waste production	No
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.33 Italy: INTERNATIONAL SISLEY TOUR

■ Profile:

SME Code	20
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)

Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.34 Italy: Dimsiway Srl - Hotel Ibis Styles Catania Acireale

■ Profile:

SME Code	24
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.35 Italy: Mistral di Alberto Sanna & C Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	33
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)

Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
Energy conservation	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.36 Italy: Hotel Village Suvaki

■ Profile:

SME Code	107
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	50 to 249
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
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ISO 14001	Adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.37 Italy: Faroo

■ Profile:

SME Code	22
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted

Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.38 Italy: Sarecen Sands Hotel

■ Profile:

SME Code	25
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	50 to 249
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted

ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes

Energy conservation	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.39 Italy: Rimini Bene Srl - Hotel Aqua

■ Profile:

SME Code	116
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted

Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes

	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.40 Italy: GEA Ambiente e Turismo Scarl

■ Profile:

SME Code	127
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted

Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications) Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	No
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	No
	Diversifying its energy sources	No
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	No
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes

Water conservation	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.41 Italy: Hotel Sporting Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	123
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	2 to 10 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes

Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.42 Italy: B&B da Vi.Vi

■ Profile:

SME Code	149
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.43 Italy: Viaggi e Miraggi

■ Profile:

SME Code	40
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)

Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (below - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.44 Italy: Isola dei Mori Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	5 ³
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	No

³ SME Code from the TOURISME third SME call.

Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	No
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	No
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	No
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	No
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	No
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	No
	Preventing waste production	No
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	No
	Promoting recycling and reuse	No
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.45 Spain: Trujillo Gamez SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	3
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	10 to 49
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
Energy conservation	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
Green procurement	Saving energy in building construction	No
	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.46 Spain: Soloraid Srl

■ Profile:

SME Code	19
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (between - 6% and - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.47 Spain: Turiart

■ Profile:

SME Code	130
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)

Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.48 Spain: Suncanarias Gestion Y Marketing Sl

■ Profile:

SME Code	23
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	No
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	No
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	No
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	No

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.49 Spain: Viatges Baikal Tour SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	12
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)

Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.50 Spain: NO LIMIT EXPERIENCIAS SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	46
NACE Code	Other reservation service and related activities (NACE 79.9)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (between - 6% and - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

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Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.51 Spain: BANANA BEACH BEYOND THE SEA SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	97
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes

Reducing water consumption	No
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	No
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	No
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	No
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	No
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	No
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	No
	Preventing waste production	No
	Improving waste sorting	No
	Fighting against food waste	No
	Promoting recycling and reuse	No
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	No
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.52 Spain: Warq tourims

■ Profile:

SME Code	113
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.53 Spain: Inzulae SLU

■ Profile:

SME Code	11
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	No
Using renewable energy	Yes

Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.54 Spain: Planes Galería de Viajes

■ Profile:

SME Code	51
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
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Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.55 Spain: In Valentia

■ Profile:

SME Code	132
NACE Code	Other reservation service and related activities (NACE 79.9)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes

Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.56 Spain: ECOTURISMO O RINCÓN SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	17
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (below - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes

Diversifying its water supply	Yes
Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.57 Spain: BedAndOcean

■ Profile:

SME Code	38
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes

Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	No
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	No
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	No
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	No
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	No
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	No
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	No
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	No
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	No
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.58 Spain: ALOHA TURIA (Mercedes Cuesta Castillo)

■ Profile:

SME Code	90
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has increased more than 5%

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	No
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	No
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.59 Spain: Genuine Spain

■ Profile:

SME Code	101
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)

Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.60 Spain: Petición Balazs Companie SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	136
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (below - 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Adopted
ISO 14001	Adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	Yes
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes

Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	Yes
	Diversifying its water supply	Yes
	Optimizing pool maintenance	No

4.61 Spain: PALMA WITH PILAR

■ Profile:

SME Code	53
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NACE Code	Other reservation service and related activities (NACE 79.9)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (below – 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES – Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. Certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	Yes
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	Yes
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.62 Spain: DYADYA VANYA, SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	98
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (between – 6% and – 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES – Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. Certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

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Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.63 Spain: Balaena Travel

■ Profile:

SME Code	4
NACE Code	Travel agency and tour operator activities (NACE 79.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover has decreased (below – 30%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES – Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. Certifications)	No

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	No
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Implementing a carbon offset system	No
Contract with or choose only green accommodations	No

Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	No
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Developing sustainable tours	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes

4.64 Spain: Canarian Hospitality, SL

■ Profile:

SME Code	4 ⁴
NACE Code	Hotels and similar accommodation (NACE 55.1)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES – Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. Certifications)	Yes

⁴ SME Code from the TOURISME third SME call.

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	Yes
Monitoring energy consumption	No
Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	No
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	Yes
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	Yes
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	No
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	No
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes

Recycling and using greywater	Yes
Diversifying its water supply	Yes
Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

4.65 Spain: Dreaming my way

■ Profile:

SME Code	7 ⁵
NACE Code	Holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE 55.2)
Number of Employees	< 10
Annual Turnover in 2019	< 2 M€
Turnover from 2018 to 2019	turnover was stable (+/- 5%)

■ Status of Certification:

ISO 9001	Not adopted
ISO 14001	Not adopted
ISO 22000	Not adopted
ISO 50001	Not adopted
ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001	Not adopted
EMAS	Not adopted
EU Ecolabel	Not adopted
Green Globe	Not adopted
Green Key	Not adopted
Nordic Swan	Not adopted
Blue Angel	Not adopted
NF Environment	Not adopted
ECORISMO	Not adopted
Legambiente Turismo	Not adopted
BIO HOTELS d'Italia	Not adopted
AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero	Not adopted
HES – Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles	Not adopted
Will participate in Activity 3 (access to env. Certifications)	Yes

■ Sustainable Practices Already Implemented:

Formulation of a sustainable policy or management plan	Yes
Assessment of organization's carbon footprint	No
Reducing energy consumption	Yes
Using renewable energy	No
Monitoring energy consumption	Yes

⁵ SME Code from the TOURISME third SME call.

Reducing water consumption	Yes
Monitoring water consumption	Yes
Reusing water and/or wastewater	No
Reducing plastic use	Yes
Reducing food waste	No
Recycling waste	Yes
Reusing furniture, small appliances, and amenities	No
Using materials made of recycled products	Yes
Monitoring waste production	Yes
Promoting sustainable mobility	No
Training staff on sustainability issues	No

■ Sustainable Practices to be Implemented within TOURISME:

Awareness and behavioral change	Raising awareness of visitors	Yes
	Raising awareness of employees	Yes
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	Knowing its carbon footprint	Yes
	Implementing a carbon offset system	Yes
	Promoting social engagement	Yes
	Promoting eco-friendly activities	Yes
Energy conservation	Knowing its energy consumption	Yes
	Modifying lighting equipment	Yes
	Upgrading household equipment and optimizing their uses	Yes
	Optimizing heating and ventilation management system	Yes
	Diversifying its energy sources	Yes
	Saving energy in building construction	Yes
Green procurement	Changing cleaning products, using ecological labels	Yes
	Developing short circuits and responsible consumption	Yes
	Promoting reuse and products made of recycled materials	Yes
	Purchasing efficient household equipment	Yes
Sustainable mobility	Promoting eco-mobility	Yes
Waste management	Knowing its waste volume	Yes
	Preventing waste production	Yes
	Improving waste sorting	Yes
	Fighting against food waste	Yes
	Promoting recycling and reuse	Yes
Water conservation	Knowing its water consumption	Yes
	Reducing its consumption	Yes
	Recycling and using greywater	No
	Diversifying its water supply	No
	Optimizing pool maintenance	Yes

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TOURISME

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